

Welcome!

We are excited to welcome your organisation to the community of Partner Organisations at The Carpentries! This document is intended to help you start using your Partnership, connect with other Partner organisations, and answer any questions you may have.

Where Do I Get Started?

Glad you asked! Here are a few things we recommend to everyone:

- **[Review the Code of Conduct](#)**: We are dedicated to providing a welcoming and supportive environment for all people. By participating in this community, you agree to abide by our Code of Conduct.
- If you have not done so already, **[schedule an onboarding session!](#)** In this 30-minute session, a Core Team member will share information and tips about how to make the best use of your Partnership. This is also an excellent opportunity to have any questions answered.

Centrally-Organised Workshops (if included in Partnership)

All Carpentries Lesson Programs ([Data Carpentry](#), [Library Carpentry](#), and [Software Carpentry](#)) offer workshops in-person or online facilitated by trained Instructors.

Using your Centrally-Organised Workshops

- **[Review our Curricula List](#)**: This is a detailed description of all available options for Centrally-Organised Workshops, to help you identify which best suits your community. If you are unsure which option is best, submit a [workshop inquiry](#) and the Workshop and Instruction Team will help you.
- **Identify Proposed Dates**: Identify a few date options at least 2-3+ months in the future.
- **[Submit Workshop Request Form](#)**: Centrally-Organised workshops must be requested at least 2-3 months before your desired workshop date.

Once the form is submitted, a workshop administrator will contact you with further details and begin the recruitment process. If the workshop date needs to be adjusted, the workshop administrator will work with you to reschedule the event.

Self-Organised Workshops

You may also [self-organise](#) unlimited Carpentries workshops with no additional workshop fee. Please complete the [self-organised workshop form](#) to notify us of your planned workshop so we can add it to our website and provide survey results.

Instructor Training (if included in Partnership)

Instructor Training events are offered as two full-day or four-half-day training sessions and are offered multiple times per month across various time zones. Your trainees are invited to attend any event that suits their schedule(s), either as a group or as individuals.

Using your Instructor Training Seats

- **Share Registration Information:** Send an email or other communication to those you would like to register for training, including the [registration steps](#) and your Partnership registration code.
Note: The Partnership registration code is unique to each Partnership and was shared with Partner contacts via email.
- **Follow-Up or Check-In:** Occasionally, you should follow up with your trainees on their progress toward certification.

Relevant Resources

- [Trainee Recruitment - Email Template](#): provides suggested language for a call within your organisation to identify who is interested in becoming an Instructor.
- [Selected Trainee Information - Email Template](#): provides selected trainees with instructions on how to register and prepare for Instructor Training.
- [Information for Partner Organisations - Instructor Training](#): provides some recommendations on selecting trainees and other information about the Instructor Training program.

Attendance Policy

We ask that trainees cancel at least one week before their Instructor Training event to allow others to use those seats. For more information, please refer to our full [Attendance Policy](#).

- **No-Show:** If the trainee does not cancel before the event and does not attend training, this is considered a 'No Show', and the seat will be marked as used. If the trainee follows up to share extenuating circumstances by emailing instructor.training@carpentries.org within 7 days of a No-Show, we will return the seat to the Partnership so the individual can reschedule training.
- **Partial Absences:** Trainees who miss more than 1 hour of an Instructor Training event may be marked absent. If a trainee misses more than 4 hours of a training event, this will be considered an incomplete training, and the seat will be marked as used. Instead of missing the event, please have the trainee cancel and reschedule for a time that better fits their schedule.

Learner-Centered Teaching (if included in Partnership)

Learner-Centered Teaching equips participants with the strategies and tools necessary to use effective, hands-on teaching practices in short-format training. This 8-hour interactive program introduces key principles of Educational Psychology and evidence-based teaching. Through a blend of short lessons and hands-on practice, participants develop their instructional skills while engaging with a cohort of peers who share their interest in teaching and learning.

Target audience

This training is intended for individuals who facilitate education for adult learners in any capacity, but with a focus on those leading short-format training. It is appropriate for both novice instructors seeking foundational skills and experienced educators aiming to enhance their practice with evidence-based, inclusive teaching strategies.

What you will learn

The goals of this training include:

- Introduce you to evidence-based teaching practices.
- Teach you strategies to foster positive, inclusive learning environments.
- Provide opportunities to practice and receive feedback on teaching techniques.
- Prepare you to lead effective short-format training sessions.

By the end of this training, participants will:

- Understand and be able to apply core concepts from educational research.
- Recognise the importance of creating respectful and inclusive learning environments, and know how to apply related policies and practices.
- Gain experience with the lesson delivery and assessment methods most effective in short-format workshops.

Using your Learner-Centred Teaching Seats

- **Share Registration Information:** Send an email or other communication to those you would like to register for training, including the [registration steps](#) and your Partnership registration code. *Note: The Partnership registration code is unique to each Partnership and was shared with Partner contacts via email.*
- **Follow-Up or Check-In:** Occasionally, you should follow up with your trainees on their experiences during the training.

Collaborative Lesson Development Training (if included in Partnership)

Collaborative Lesson Development Training teaches essential skills and good practices for designing and developing a lesson as an open source project. The training will guide you through the design process and initial development of a new lesson, prepare you to work with the infrastructure we use to build accessible, open-source lesson websites, and provide some advice and techniques for effective collaboration on the project. [Visit the training curriculum.](#)

Using your Collaborative Lesson Development Training Seats

- **Share Registration Information:** Visit the [Collaborative Lesson Development Training](#) calendar to view a list of upcoming training events. [Contact the Curriculum Team](#) to register for one of the listed events, quoting the registration code. *Note: The Partnership registration code is unique to each Partnership and was shared with Partner contacts via email.*

- **Follow-Up or Check-In:** Occasionally, you should follow up with your trainees on their progress.

Professional Development Courses (if included in Partnership)

Our Professional Development courses help individuals and teams keep their skills up-to-date for the rapidly evolving digital workplace with focused training in remote collaboration, effective meeting facilitation, and more. Each course is 2-3 hours in length, and can be attended by individuals or cohorts. Initial course offerings include GitHub Skills, Running Effective Online Meetings, and Effective Collaboration for Remote Teams, with additional courses to be introduced over the coming year.

Using your Professional Development Seats

- **Share Registration Information:** Send an email or other communication to those you would like to register for the course, including the [registration](#) steps and your Partnership registration code. *Note: The Partnership registration code is unique to each Partnership and was shared with Partner contacts via email.*
- **Follow-Up or Check-In:** Occasionally, you should follow up with your trainees on their progress.

Partner Contact(s)

Partner contacts are the main point of contact for your Partnership. Partner Contacts receive important information and updates about the Partnership. Partner Contacts may request Partnership data (such as additional copies of survey data or trainee progress), request workshops, or initiate a renewal of the Partnership. We recommend that each Partnership have **at least two** Partner contacts.

- Update your Partnership contacts at any time by emailing partnership@carpentries.org.

Partnership Mailing List

Partner Contacts are automatically added to The Carpentries Partnership mailing list. Partner contacts will receive announcements and information relevant to all Partner Organisations via this mailing list.

Quarterly Updates

The Carpentries keeps you updated on your Partnership usage by sending an email update to Partner contacts every three months (from the Partnership's start date). The update will include detailed information on benefit usage and a list of trainee progress toward Instructor certification (if applicable). This email is a nice reminder to request workshops and/or follow up with your trainees working toward Instructor Certification.

Additional Resources

- [Partner Frequently Asked Questions](#)
- [Welcome Tip Sheet for New Community Partners](#)
- [Our Community Glossary](#)

Questions

If you have questions, please get in touch with our team by emailing partnership@carpentries.org or [scheduling a meeting](#).

Citing and reusing this tipsheet

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